

COGNITIVE VALUE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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ABSTRACT: This article defines the cognitive value of phraseological gisms, the phraseological fund of the Russian language is considered. Evaluated assessment of the value paradigm of the Russian linguocultural community. Various examples are given. The significance and relevance of ness of cognitive activity of phraseological units.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В данной статье определяется познавательное значение фразеологизмов, рассматривается фразеологический фонд русского языка. Оценочная оценка ценностной парадигмы русского лингвокультурного сообщества. Приводятся различные примеры. Значение и актуальность познавательной деятельности фразеологических единиц.

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada frazeologik birliklarning kognitiv ma'nosi aniqlanadi, rus tilining frazeologik fondi ko'rib chiqiladi. Rus lingvomadaniy hamjamiyatining qiymat paradigmasini taxminiy baholash. Turli misollar keltiriladi. Frazeologik birliklarning bilish faoliyatining mazmuni va dolzarbligi.

KEY WORDS: cognitive value, phraseological gisms, expressive sayings, figurative sayings, historicalera, stable comparisons, phraseological units, paraphrases,distinctive features, combinations.

INTRODUCTION.

The Russian language is diverse and interesting. Phraseological units contain a significant part of our cultural and historical heritage, we absorb phraseological units with mother's milk, probably. The richness of a language is the richness of its phraseology, i.e. expressive and figurative sayings, mouths, well-aimed and winged words. Very often, such words and turns lie the whole world, the historical era - the

facts of the bygone life of the ideas and beliefs of our ancestors, the real events of the distant past. As we know, it contains not only individual words denoting the realities of the surrounding reality, but also "whole" soldered phrases, which are called phraseological units. The latter are the same independent linguistic units as words.

METHODS: Phraseologisms consist of at least two words that mean something of a single meaning, for example: among them one can distinguish stable comparisons (like a bath leaf, like on pins and needles, like a cow licked with its tongue, like a saddle for a cow), metaphorical epithets (tinned throat, iron grasp), hyperbole (mountains of gold, a sea of pleasure as far as the eye can see), litotes (with a poppy seed, grasping at straws). There are also phraseological units that are periphrases, that is, descriptive figurative expressions that replace one word: distant lands - 'far', there are not enough stars from the sky - 'narrow', oblique fathom in the shoulders - 'mighty, strong' .

Some phraseological units owe their expressiveness to a pun, a joke underlying them: a hole from a donut, from a sleeve vest, not himself, a week without a year, slaughter without a knife. The expressiveness of others is based on the play of antonyms: neither alive nor dead, neither give nor take, not a candle to God, not a poker to hell, more or less; on the clash of synonyms: from the fire to the frying pan, the mind has gone beyond the mind, to pour from empty to empty, around and around. Phraseological units give speech a special expressiveness and folk-colloquial coloring. Phraseological combinations are stable turns, the meaning of which is motivated by the semantics of their constituent components, one of which has a phraseologically related meaning: look down (head) (there are no stable phrases "down your hand", "down your foot" in the language). The verb to lower in the meaning of 'lower' has a phraseologically related meaning and does not combined. Another example: a sensitive issue (situation, position, circumstance). The adjective delicate means 'requiring great discretion, tact', but the possibilities of its compatibility are limited: one cannot say "delicious proposal", "delicious decision", etc.

RESULTS.

As you can see, the meaning of a phraseological unit often does not follow from the meaning of each individual word that is part of it. A phraseological unit has no

common features with a free phrase. Any phrase is a combination of lexemes in which they retain their features, while the components of a phraseological unit lose all the features of an independent word, except for the sound image: lexical meaning, forms of change, syntactic function. Connections and relationships between words in the composition of a phraseological unit are close and soldered.

Thus, a phraseological unit is a figurative expression that is stable in composition and structure and consists of two or more words. What are the characteristics of phraseological units?

DISCUSSION.

As an independent lexical unit of the language, phraseological units have their own distinctive features:

1. they contain two or more words, for example: play on nerves - intentionally annoy, annoy someone; sewn with white threads - fakeness, artificiality of something is visible; grab at straws - use any, often dubious means to get out of a difficult situation; seven Fridays a week - about someone who often changes their plans; to beat like a fish on ice - to fight need, to live in poverty;

2. Phraseologisms have a stable composition.

This means that the phrase cannot be distorted, a new word inserted into it or one word replaced by another, since phraseological units arose as a result of long-term folk art and over many centuries of their use, like faceted polished crystals, they acquired their clearly defined composition. For example, in the stable phrase “hang in the air”, which means “to be in an unclear, indefinite position”, we will change the words: propagate in the air (sound wave); hang on a rope.

As a result of our language experiment, phraseologism crumbled like a house of cubes, if you pull one of them out of this children's building. The verb "hang", used in the newly formed phrase, has lost its figurative meaning, and the phraseological unit no longer exists.

3. Reproducibility

Perhaps this sign is one of the main ones. Phraseological units are not created each time anew at the will of the speaker, but are used in a speech situation as ready-made "bricks" for building figurative and expressive speech.

There will be your brothers with capital! Will. That's just me so nothing to stay - it's true! Yes, I flew out, brother, I'm in the pipe! (M. E. Saltykov-Shchedrin). His brother embellished his dry presentation with details so picturesque that the chairman, who was already beginning to calm down, pricked up his ears again (I. Ilf and E. Petrov). Look, bastard, started a hurdy-gurdy, what are you, Petka, a woman or what? (A. Blok).

The use of phraseological units is a distinctive feature of N.V. Gogol.

The analysis of the writer's works made it possible to deduce the patterns of use of phraseological units in his texts, determine their role and compile a dictionary of Gogol's phraseological combinations.

4. Phraseologisms have a figurative meaning that has developed historically.

Sometimes the figurative meaning of a phraseological unit cannot be understood without referring to the history of its occurrence.

For example: the stable phrase "you can't drive up on a goat" is difficult for many to understand. What is a goat and why should (or shouldn't) be ridden? This stable expression is associated with the speech of jesters and buffoons, who, while amusing the people at the bright stamps and holidays, dressed up as a goat, a bear, a devil, etc. Their repertoire included riding a goat or a pig. But especially important and gloomy people, even this trick did not work: they did not even smile, looking at such folk fun. Since then, they say "you can't drive up on a goat" about impregnable, proud, important or cool people. No, brother, not everyone poke their nose at him. Sometimes it is so steep that you can't drive up on a goat (A. Bestuzhev-Marlinsky). And I teased Anton that he would study among solid geniuses and imagine himself a genius, and then you wouldn't drive up to him even on a goat (L. Uvarova).

5. Phraseologisms are one member of the sentence

In a sentence, a phraseological unit is not divided into parts, but is entirely one member of the sentence. Today we worked up a sweat. We (what were we doing?)

worked up a sweat. Phraseologism "worked up a sweat" is used as a predicate. There are people in life so close in spirit that they say about them that they are made from the same dough. Similarly, in this sentence, the set phrase "from one test" is part of the predicate.

So, phraseological units make our speech figurative and lively. But one of the main properties of phraseological units, as I think, is figurativeness. Imagery is the basis of many phraseological units.

After all, the study of speech phraseology introduces us to the laboratory of the people - the language creator, and it is no coincidence that writers who see it in Russian phraseology study it with such attention.

CONCLUSION.

The picturesqueness and figurativeness of speech acts with poetic phraseological units on the listener's imagination, forcing him to experience what was said more strongly than if the speaker addressed him with an ugly, purely logical speech. With the help of phraseological units, not only the content of the statement is transmitted, but also the feelings of a person.

Imagery is achieved by combining two phenomena, of which one becomes the basis, and the second is compared with it.

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